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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The Indices of Social Development (ISD), developed by the International Institute of Social Studies (ISS), provide a comprehensive dataset for assessing social development across 222 countries from 1990 to 2020 (as of August 2025). By aggregating 275 indicators from 30 sources, the ISD capture six key dimensions: 1) Civic Activism, 2) Clubs and Associations, 3) Intergroup Cohesion, 4) Interpersonal Safety and Trust, 5) Gender Equality, and 6) Inclusion of Minorities. Using the nonparametric matching percentiles method, the ISD mitigate biases from small samples and incomplete data, while applying five-year averages to reduce outlier effects. Despite innovations, limitations remain, including reliance on national-level data, multi-year smoothing, and single-source dependencies in some indices. Recent updates expand coverage and integrate digital activism, but structural challenges persist. The ISD offer valuable, publicly accessible tools for comparative and longitudinal analysis, while requiring critical reflection on data completeness and interpretative limits.

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Data Review – Indices of Social Development (ISD)

The Indices of Social Development (ISD), hosted by the International Institute of Social Studies (ISS), provide a comprehensive set of indicators designed to measure social development across countries and over time (7). Social development, broadly understood as “putting people at the centre of development” (7), has become increasingly recognised since the 1990s as central to – among others – “sustainable economic growth” (7).

To overcome past limitations in international comparative research on social development, the ISD aggregate 275 individual indicators from 30 sources and cover 222 countries at five-year intervals between 1990 and 2020 (as of August 2025) (7). These indicators cover the six key dimensions: Civic Activism, Clubs and Associations, Intergroup Cohesion, Interpersonal Safety and Trust, Gender Equality, and Inclusion of Minorities (7). Together, they offer nuanced insight into the norms, beliefs, and behaviours that shape human well-being and institutional functioning beyond economic variables.

Methodological Foundation

The ISD uses the matching percentiles method developed by Prof. Dr. Johann Graf Lambsdorff for the Corruption Perceptions Index, in which “values are matched across cases based on country ranking” (11). This nonparametric method aggregates data by ranking country values across indicators rather than relying on linear assumptions (11). This approach allows indicators to be repeatedly added to refine the index over time, even when sample sizes are small or coverage is partial (11). As such, unlike regression-based techniques, matching percentiles can handle small sample sizes and incomplete data coverage without inducing bias (11).

Formally, each indicator y_i is assumed to reflect a latent social development value L_i , transformed by an unknown function f and subject to measurement error ε_i (11):

$$y_i = f(L_i) + \varepsilon_i$$

Since it is not possible “to estimate the functional form f , the aggregation methodology is nonparametric” (11), but it is assumed that countries’ relative positions on y “reflect[] a better or worse underlying condition with respect to L ” (11).

Importantly, five-year averages are used instead of annual data to minimise sampling errors and mitigate the effects of outliers (5).

Critiques

According to De Haan et al. (2011) the ISD represent an innovation in quantifying aspects of development (De Haan et al. 2011: 9), but they also identify limitations that users should keep in mind. At the time, concerns included the absence of sub-national

coverage and the restriction to multi-year averages, which limit temporal precision (De Haan et al. 2011: 11). The 2025 ISD release still uses five-year averages and remains country-level only (5). While in 2011 the diversity and quality of the sources varied – coverage has since expanded from over 200 indicators from 25 sources to 275 indicators from 30 sources across 222 countries, although certain indices (e.g., Clubs and Associations) still depend on single sources in some cases (De Haan et al. 2011: 4, 11; 7).

De Haan et al. (2011) also stressed conceptual and definitional challenges, particularly in measuring inter-group cohesion, where aggregated scores might mask rapid shifts towards exclusionary attitudes or discrimination (De Haan et al. 2011: 19). In the current ISD the five-year smoothing and reliance on perceptions (5) still limit sensitivity to short-term changes. Furthermore, the 2011 critique noted the oversight of emerging forms of activity such as digital mobilisation or the “increased use of social media” (De Haan et al. 2011: 14), which the 2025 Civic Activism index now partially includes through measures of online petitions, political organising, and digital engagement (4). Finally, while correlations between ISD dimensions and outcomes such as economic growth are promising, De Haan et al. (2011) caution that these do not establish causality (De Haan et al. 2011: 12-13) – a point that remains valid in the 2025 dataset.

As this paper was published in 2011, its assessment does not reflect the expanded coverage, added indicators, or incorporation of digital activism in later ISD versions, but many structural limitations it identified – temporal resolution, national-level aggregation, and some single-source dependencies – persist.

Using the ISD

The ISD database is publicly accessible (4). Data can be downloaded in both .csv and .xlsx formats, either both with indices and indicators or solely with indices (4). The downloads provide both data with and without standard errors (4). However, for some indices such as Clubs and Associations, standard errors are not provided due to limitations in source diversity – e.g., reliance solely on the World Values Survey in certain cases (5).

Users can customise their data download by filtering by specific indices, year (1990-2020 in five-year intervals), and countries (4). This flexible interface allows for both comparative and longitudinal studies. For instance, data coverage for countries like Georgia and Estonia spans all indices and years, whereas countries like Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan have limited coverage in certain indices (4, see table 2). The detailed overview in the following Table 1 reflects the variety and depth of the indicators used for each index. For example, Civic Activism is measured using 14 indicators ranging from media consumption (radio, TV, newspaper) and petition participation to digital political engagement (e.g. online petitions or political actions), derived from Afrobarometer, World Values Surveys (WVS), and others (2).

Table 1: Indices, Indicators, Sources and Countries covered by the ISD (as of August 2025)

Indices	Indicators	Source of Indicator	Countries
Civic Activism (2)	1) Attended a demonstration or protest march (Yes/No, but would do if I had the chance)	Afrobarometer	34
	2) “How often do you listened to radio news?” (Percentage “every day” or “several times in the last week”)	Afrobarometer	34
	3) Proportion of mobile cellular telephone subscriptions	International Telecommunications Union	181
	4) “How often do you watch TV news?” (Percentage “every day” or “several times in the last week”)	Afrobarometer	34
	5) “How often do you read newspaper news?”. (Percentage “every day” or “several times in the last week”)	Afrobarometer	41
	6) Per 1000 adults, how many people buy a newspaper daily?	Sustainable Governance Indicators	41
	7) Have actually signed a petition or might do it?	World Values Surveys (WVS)	64
	8) Have actually joined a boycott or might do it?	WVS	73
	9) Have actually attended peaceful demonstrations or might do it?	WVS	73
	10) Did you search information about politics and political events online?	WVS	42
	11) Did you encourage other people to take any form of political action online?	WVS	40
	12) Have actually signed an electronic petition or might do it?	WVS	41
	13) Have you organized online political activities, events, protests?	WVS	40
	14) In the last 12 months, have you participated in a public protest or meetings of political movements and parties?	Afrobarometer	9
Clubs and Associations (3)	1) Are you an active member of a church or religious organization?	WVS	45
	2) Are you an active member of a sports or recreational organization?	WVS	44
	3) Are you an active member of a voluntary organization?	WVS	44
	4) Are you an active member of a women’s group?	WVS	43
	5) Are you an active member of a art organization?	WVS	44
	6) Are you an active member of a trade union? (Percentage saying yes)	WVS	44
	7) Are you an active member of a political party?	WVS	44

	8) Are you an active member of an environmental organization?	WVS	44
	9) Are you an active member of a professional organization?	WVS	44
	10) Would you say that family is very important in life?	WVS	73
	11) Would you say that friends are very important in life?	WVS	73
	12) Would you say that religion is very important in life?	WVS	73
	13) Are you an active member of a labour union?	WVS	44
	14) Are you an active member of a labour union or self-help group?	WVS	43
	15) Are you an active member of a political party or humanitarian organization?	WVS	43
	16) Are you a leader or active member of a religious group?	Afrobarometer	34
	17) Are you a leader or active member of a development association?	Afrobarometer	34
	18) Did you attended a community meeting in the past year? (All respondents “Yes” or “Would do if I had the chance”)	Afrobarometer	34
	19) “If you were in trouble, do you have relatives or friends you can count on to help you whenever you need them?”	World Happiness Report-Gallup	145
	20) Attendance at meeting of Community Improvement Group/Community Council Meetings	Americas Barometer	10
	21) Attendance at Meetings of Women’s Group	Americas Barometer	7
	22) Attendance at Meetings of Religious Organization	Americas Barometer	10
	23) “Important to help people and care for others well-being” (1 for respondents “very much like me” and “like me”)	European Social Survey (ESS)	29
	24) How often do you meet socially with friends, relatives or work colleagues?	ESS	29
	25) Are you an active member of a labour union?	Afrobarometer	16
	26) Percentage membership of a voluntary organization	Latino-barometer	18
Inter-group Cohesion (9)	1) Do you have confidence in the local police force, feel safe walking alone at night, had money or property stolen or have you been assaulted or mugged?	World Happiness Report-Gallup	134
	2) Rating of differences of opinion on major political issues in this society	V-Dem	177
	3) Log riots per log capita	Cross-National Time-Series Data Archive (CNTS)	132

	4) Log instances of guerrilla conflict per log capita	CNTS	56
	5) Terrorist coded attacks based on a weighted average of the last four years (2016-2019) of 9 types	Global Terrorism Database	138
	6) Global Peace Index rating on deaths in organized conflict at least 25	Uppsala Conflict Data Program	38
	7) Fund for Peace rating on the “legacy of vengeance-seeking group grievance or group paranoia”	Fund for Peace/Fragile States Index	178
	8) Average values of all indicators of the International Country Risk Guide	International Country Risk Guide (ICRG)	138
	9) Level of internal conflict, International Country Risk Guide rating	ICRG	140
	10) Risk of terrorism, International Country Risk Guide rating	IEP Global Terrorism Index	134
Inter-personal Safety and Trust (10)	1) Frequency of alcohol consumed on the streets in our neighbourhood	WVS	42
	2) How much do you trust your family? (“not very much” or “not at all”)	WVS	73
	3) How much do you trust people you meet for the first time?” (“not very much” or “not at all”)	WVS	73
	4) Are you satisfied with your freedom to choose what you do with your life?	World Happiness Report-Gallup	144
	5) Felt unsafe in home, proportion saying ‘never’	Afrobarometer	34
	6) Had stuff stolen from home, proportion saying ‘never’	Afrobarometer	34
	7) Africa, % have not been attacked	Afrobarometer	34
	8) Feel Safe in their Area at Night	ESS	40
	9) Preferred not to go out at night	WVS	42
	10) Theft of a motorized land vehicle, police recorded offences, rates per 100,000 population	United Nations Office On Drugs and Crime (UNODC)	60
	11) Theft, police recorded offences, rates per 100,000 population	UNODC	74
	12) Sexual Exploitation, rates per 100,000 inhabitants	UNODC	44
	13) Have you, or someone in your family, been assaulted, attacked, or victim of crime in the last 12 months? (Percentage)	Latino-barometer	18
	14) Generally speaking, would you say that most people can be trusted or that your can’t be too careful in dealing with people?	Latino-barometer	18
	15) Frequency in your neighborhood: drug sale in street (values of very and quite frequently)	WVS	42

	16) Frequency of robberies in the neighbourhood (values of very and quite frequently)	WVS	42
	17) Have you been victim of any type of crime in the past 12 months? Frequency in the neighbourhood of robberies	Americas Barometer	43
	18) Have you been victim of any type of crime in the past 12 months?	UNODC	5
	19) Kidnapping Rate	UNODC	65
	20) Homicide Estimates by country	World Health Organization (WHO)	183
	21) WHO homicide rate	WHO	183
	22) How much do you trust people you know personally? (“not very much” or “not at all”)	WVS	73
Gender Equality (6)	1) When jobs are scarce, men should have more right to a job than women	WVS	73
	2) On the whole, men make better politicians	WVS	73
	3) A university education is more important for a boy than for a girl	WVS	73
	4) % Managers, “Men better Executives than Women”	WVS	73
	5) On the whole, men make better leaders	WVS	73
	6) Women have the same capabilities than me for science and technology	Latino-barometer	18
	7) Women should have the same chance of being elected to political office as men	Afrobarometer	34
	8) Africa, % Man has “Right to Beat Wife”	Afrobarometer	34
	9) Discrimination in family-law	Sub-index of SIGI	177
	10) Discrimination in civil liberties	Sub-index of SIGI	139
	11) Discrimination in physical integrity	Sub-index of SIGI	128
	12) Discrimination in women’s rights to access to economic resources	Sub-index of SIGI	133
	13) Ratio of average female to male wages, across all available labor categories	International Labour Organization (ILO)	75
	14) Problem if women have more income than husband?	WVS	42
	15) Ratio of female to male labor force participation rate, right censored at 1	World Development Indicators (WDI)	186
	16) Female-Male Primary Enrollment Ratio	WDI	137
	17) Female-Male Secondary Enrollment Ratio	WDI	125
	18) Female-Male Tertiary Enrollment Ratio	WDI	117
	19) Ratio of female to male mortality rates, left-censored at 0.66	WDI	165
	20) Ratio of females among legislators, senior officials and managers	ILO	30

	21) Ratio of females in professional jobs	ILO	54
	22) Would you say your gross pay is unfairly low, fair, or unfairly high? Only women answers	ESS	29
	23) Tradition is important to her. She tries to follow the customs. Only women respondents	ESS	29
	24) Number of states with a female head of state	UN Women	156
	25) Percent of labour force that is female	WDI	156
	26) Ratio of females among legislators, senior officials and managers	ILO	94
	27) In your country, for similar work, to what extent are wages for women equal to those of men? Managers survey	World Economic Forum (Executive Opinion Survey)	138
	28) Percentage of female ministers	UN Women	156
	29) Percentage of female parliamentarians	UN Women	156
Inclusion of Minorities (8)	1) Do you trust people of another religion?	WVS	73
	2) Do you trust people of another nationality?	WVS	73
	3) Could you please sort out any that you would not like to have as neighbors? People of a different race.	WVS	73
	4) Could you please mention any that you would not like to have as neighbors? People who have AIDS	WVS	43
	5) Could you please sort out any that you would not like to have as neighbors? Homosexuals	WVS	71
	6) Could you please sort out any that you would not like to have as neighbors? People of a different religion	WVS	43
	7) Could you please sort out any that you would not like to have as neighbors? People of a different language	WVS	43
	8) Statement: Jobs are scarce, employers should give priority to (nation) people than immigrants	WVS	59
	9) Foreign/Native Labour Participation, Intermediate Education	OECD	33
	10) Foreign/Native Labour Participation, Low Education	OECD	33
	11) Native Labour Participation, High Education	OECD	33
	12) Are people treated unequally under the law?	Afrobarometer	13
	13) Economic Inequality between groups	Fund for Peace/Fragile States Index	178
	14) Level of ethnic tensions, rating	ICRG	140
	15) Level of religious tensions, rating	ICRG	140
	16) Group Political Risk Rating	ICRG	138
	17) To what extent do you think [country] should allow people of the same race or ethnic group as most [country]'s people to come and live here	ESS	28
	18) To what extent do you think [country] should allow people of a different race or ethnic group come and live here	ESS	28

	19) To what extent do you think [country] should allow people from poorer countries outside Europe come and live here	ESS	29
	20) Would you say it is generally bad or good for [country]’s economy that people come to live here from other countries?	ESS	29
	21) Would you say that [country]’s cultural life is generally undermined by people coming to live here from other countries?	ESS	29
	22) Is [country] made a worse or a better place for the economy by people coming to live here from other countries?	ESS	29

(sources: **2; 3; 6; 8; 9; 10**)

The ISD provides relatively broad country coverage for the regions relevant to Discuss Data (see Table 2), including countries in Eastern Europe, the Caucasus, and Central Asia. However, coverage varies significantly across indices and years. While countries such as Estonia, Georgia, Latvia, Lithuania, and the Russian Federation show consistently high coverage across all six indices and nearly all time points, others like Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan have limited or missing data for key indices such as Clubs and Associations and Inclusion of Minorities (3; 4; 8). Additionally, Kazakhstan and Tajikistan display gaps in the Civic Activism (2; 4), and Interpersonal Safety and Trust (4; 10) indices for several time periods.

The use of five-year averages facilitates comparability over time by smoothing out gaps and minimising the effects of “outliers caused by extreme scores for one point in time” (5) or missing annual data (5). Still, comparability across countries must be approached cautiously: while the matching percentiles method helps align rankings (11), underlying data is drawn from diverse sources and vary in availability and sample size. In some cases, such as the Clubs and Associations index, reliance on a single source like the World Values Sources for certain countries (3; 5) limits the robustness and reliability of county-level comparisons. These inconsistencies underline the importance of critically assessing data completeness before conducting cross-country comparisons or longitudinal analyses using the ISD.

Table 2: Discuss Data Relevant Country Coverage (as of August 2025)

Country	Indices covered	Years covered (total indicator – not necessarily all indicators are covered; data may be available for the years 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020)
Armenia	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 2010, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2015

	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005
Azerbaijan	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 1995, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 2000
Belarus	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990
Estonia	Civic Activism	All years covered
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	All years covered
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	All years covered
Georgia	Civic Activism	All years covered
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000
	Clubs and Associations	All years covered
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	All years covered
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005
Kazakhstan	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2020 Not covered: 2005, 2010, 2015
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995

	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000
Kyrgyz Republic	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2015
Latvia	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015 Not covered: 2020
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010 Not covered: 2015, 2020
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	All years covered
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	All years covered
Lithuania	Civic Activism	All years covered
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	All years covered
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
Moldova	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010 Not covered: 2015, 2020
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010 Not covered: 2015, 2020
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015

Russian Federation		Not covered: 2020
	Intergroup Cohesion	All years covered
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015 Not covered: 2020
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	All years covered
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	All years covered
Tajikistan	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2020 Not covered: 2005, 2010, 2015
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2015
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015
Turkmenistan	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010 Not covered: 2015, 2020
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000
	Clubs and Associations	No data
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	No data
Ukraine	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995
	Clubs and Associations	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2020 Not covered: 2015
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990
	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	Covered: 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990
Uzbekistan	Civic Activism	Covered: 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010 Not covered: 2015, 2020
	Intergroup Cohesion	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000
	Clubs and Associations	No data
	Interpersonal Safety and Trust	Covered: 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020 Not covered: 1990, 1995, 2000

	Gender Equality	All years covered
	Inclusion of Minorities	No data

(source: 4)

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The ISD is hosted by the ISS, which is part of the Erasmus University Rotterdam. There is no publicly available information on the ISD website regarding its funding.

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Sources

- (1) De Haan A/Van Staveren I/Webbink E/Foa R (2011): The last mile in analysing well-being and poverty: Indices of Social Development. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Working Paper No. 2011-03.
- (2) ISD (n.d.): Civic Activism. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/home/civic-activism/> (accessed 17.07.2025).
- (3) ISD (n.d.): Clubs and Associations. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/home/clubs-and-associations/> (accessed 17.07.2025).
- (4) ISD (n.d.): Data Access. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/data-access/> (accessed 17.07.2025).
- (5) ISD (n.d.): FAQ. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/faq/> (accessed 21.07.2025).
- (6) ISD (n.d.): Gender Equality. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/home/gender-equality/> (accessed 17.07.2025).
- (7) ISD (n.d.): Home. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/> (accessed 06.08.2025).
- (8) ISD (n.d.): Inclusion of Minorities. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/home/inclusion-of-minorities/> (accessed 18.08.2025).
- (9) ISD (n.d.): Intergroup Cohesion. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/home/intergroup-cohesion/> (accessed 17.07.2025).
- (10) ISD (n.d.): Interpersonal Safety and Trust. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/home/interpersonal-safety-and-trust/> (accessed 17.07.2025).
- (11) ISD (n.d.): Methodology. In: International Institute of Social Studies. Online available at: <https://isd.iss.nl/more-information/about-isd/methodology/> (accessed 07.08.2025).